

Influence of an Anisotropic Contribution on Stress Components in an Artery Affected by a Aneurysm in Shearing

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ABSTRACT:

In this study of contributions with shear in an artery affected by aneurysm, a kinematic is given. Some tensor, invariants and stress components were calculated. With a shear which decreases with the progression of the aneurysm, we obtain that isotropic invariants are positive. Anisotropic invariant I_4 and I_5 stay respectively positive and negative. As a big contribution in this study is that we show that the anisotropic contribution has not a big influence in the energy potential behaviour, but it has big influence in the stress components behaviour between the two models and then, fibrous reinforcement has a big influence in the capacity of resistance of arterial stress components which is true in the reality.

Keywords: Aneurysm, Elementary invariants, shear, Isotropic energy potential, anisotropic energy potential..

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INTRODUCTION

The study of shearing of elastic and incompressible materials has always been the subject of special attention in the study of mechanical systems [1]. In the study of mechanical fracture, the example of anti-planar shear has been a subject of particular interest to better understand these mechanical systems. Simple shear deformations, for which the displacement gradient is constant, are sustainable both in the linear and nonlinear theory. So that necessary and sufficient conditions on the strain energies for homogeneous isotropic nonlinear elastic materials which allow antiplane shear were obtained in Knowles for further contributions in the compressible case [2].

In the linear transversely isotropic elasticity, a study of deformation of a circular infinite hollow cylinder, whose inner surface is fixed, while its outer surface is subject to a constant axial surface traction is studied [3]. In isotropic linear elasticity, the solution of this problem is just a state of anti-plane axial shear.

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The authors show that it is possible to use an axial tension field to generate an azimuthal shear deformation. They show that this fact suggests to use anisotropy to design some elastic machines which can combine different deformation modes.

Other authors [4] have shown that this characterization of materials is closely related to the nature and form of the energy function. This characterization remains less obvious in nonlinear elasticity.

Other studies have focused on the effect of shear stress generated by a fluid in a tubular structure [5]. Their study showed that in the renal tube reduced fluid shear stress down-regulated the levels of megalin receptors, thereby reducing the renal distribution of albumin nanoparticles. Five solutions were found where two are complex which are pure imaginaries and three are reals. In the other hand the generalization of the study mean with the presence of the three isotropic invariants gives only two complex solutions, existential condition is also given. The numerical simulation of real shear solutions shows difference between them and allowed us to find that there are two real solutions which better describes the shear in a stenosis or aneurysm artery [6].

To describe the anisotropic hyperelastic mechanical behavior of a mechanical structure, it is still useful to use deformation energy functions in form polynomial, exponential, power or logarithmic. These energy potentials have been established as part of a phenomenological approach that describes the macroscopic nature of the material.

In this study of anisotropic contribution in an artery affected by aneurysm in shearing, we will set a kinematic of deformation describing those transformations obtained from the previous studies in the case of an isotropic and compressible model, we will associate a found shear and anisotropic contribution.

We will calculate some tensors, isotropic and anisotropic elementary invariants and stress components. Many of those calculated expressions will be simulated to see the influence of isotropic and anisotropic contribution in those expressions particularly in energy potential and stress components.

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

The geometric domain is a hollow cylinder composed of an elastic, isotropic or anisotropic material with an inner surface bounded by a rigid cylinder and an outer surface subjected to axial shear. In a cylindrical coordinate system, let's consider a point M which in the undeformed configuration has the components (R, θ, Z) and in the deformed configuration the components (r, θ, z) . The kinematics of deformation representing the aneurysm with the presence of shear [7,8,9] is described by:

$$r(R, Z) = R + \delta \left(1 + \cos \left(\frac{Z}{2} \right) \right); \quad -2\pi \leq Z \leq 2\pi; \quad \theta = \alpha_0 \Theta; \quad z = \gamma Z + \omega(R) \quad (1)$$

which translates for axial shear, a combined deformation of the tube: radial with $r(R)$ and longitudinal or anti-planar shear with $\omega(R)$, α_0 a parameter and γ is the elongation.

Here we set $\omega(R)$ as in [9] by:

$$\omega(R) = \frac{2R_e\sigma_0}{\mu^2 f(f-1)} \log(R) + \omega_0 \quad (2)$$

And then it follows:

$$d\omega(R) = \omega'(R) = \frac{2R_e\sigma_0}{\mu^2 f(f-1)R} \quad (3)$$

The simulation of the shear and its derivative by using:

$$Z = -2 * \pi i : \frac{\pi i}{4} : 2 * \pi i; O = Z; R = 0.001 : 0.00006 : 0.0002;$$

give:

Figure 1. Graphic Representation of $\omega(R)$

Figure 2. Graphic Representation of $d\omega(R)$

The graphics shows that the shear decreases with the progression of the aneurysm.

The simulation of the kinematic by using these same conditions give:

Figure 3. Artery with aneurysm

Figure 4. Kinematic of Transformation

According to the kinematic, we can calculate the deformation gradient tensor:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \lambda_{rz} \\ 0 & \alpha_0 \frac{r}{R} & 0 \\ \omega' & 0 & \gamma \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where r' and ω' are respectively the derivatives with respect to R of r and ω and λ_{rz} defined by $\lambda_{rz} = \partial r / \partial z$.

From the deformation gradient, we can calculate in the Eulerian configuration the left Cauchy-Green tensor defined by:

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{F}^T = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + \lambda_{rz}^2 & 0 & \omega' + \gamma\lambda_{rz} \\ 0 & (\alpha_0 \frac{r}{R})^2 & 0 \\ \omega' + \gamma\lambda_{rz} & 0 & \omega'^2 + \gamma^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & 0 & b_{13} \\ 0 & b_{22} & 0 \\ b_{31} & 0 & b_{33} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

and its inverse:

$$\mathbf{B}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\omega'^2 + \gamma^2}{(\gamma - \omega'\lambda_{rz})^2} & 0 & \frac{\omega' + \gamma\lambda_{rz}}{(\gamma - \omega'\lambda_{rz})^2} \\ 0 & \left(\frac{R}{\alpha_0 r}\right)^2 \frac{\gamma^2 + \omega'\lambda_{rz}(\omega'\lambda_{rz} - 2\gamma)}{(\gamma - \omega'\lambda_{rz})^2} & 0 \\ \frac{\omega' + \gamma\lambda_{rz}}{(\gamma - \omega'\lambda_{rz})^2} & 0 & \frac{1 + \lambda_{rz}^2}{(\gamma - \omega'\lambda_{rz})^2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} & 0 & c_{13} \\ 0 & c_{22} & 0 \\ c_{31} & 0 & c_{33} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

It's follow the adjoint of the tensor \mathbf{B} noted \mathbf{B}^* defined by $\mathbf{B}^* = \det(\mathbf{B})\mathbf{B}^{-1}$, so then:

$$\mathbf{B}^* = \begin{pmatrix} (\alpha_0 \frac{r}{R})^2 (\omega'^2 + \gamma^2) & 0 & (\alpha_0 \frac{r}{R})^2 (\omega' + \gamma\lambda_{rz}) \\ 0 & \gamma^2 + \omega'\lambda_{rz}(\omega'\lambda_{rz} - 2\gamma) & 0 \\ (\alpha_0 \frac{r}{R})^2 (\omega' + \gamma\lambda_{rz}) & 0 & (\alpha_0 \frac{r}{R})^2 (1 + \lambda_{rz}^2) \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

With the two previous tenseur we can calculate the first three elementary isotropic invariants of deformation given by:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 = \text{tr}(\mathbf{B}) &= 1 + \lambda_{rz}^2 + \left(\alpha_0 \frac{r}{R}\right)^2 + \omega'^2 + \gamma^2; \\ I_2 = \text{tr}(\mathbf{B}^*) &= \left(\alpha_0 \frac{r}{R}\right)^2 (\omega'^2 + \gamma^2 + 1 + \lambda_{rz}^2) + \gamma^2 + \omega'\lambda_{rz}(\omega'\lambda_{rz} - 2\gamma); \\ I_3 = \det(\mathbf{B}) &= \left(\alpha_0 \frac{r}{R}\right)^2 (\gamma - \omega'\lambda_{rz})^2. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The behaviours of these three isotropic invariants are set by the following graphic:

Figure 5. Third Isotropic Invariant

Figure 6. Third Isotropic Invariant

We can see here that all isotropic invariants stay positive and I_3 is negligible compared to I_1 and I_2 with I_1 greater than I_2 almost all the time excepted some values where its are equal.

In addition, to take account of deformations in preferred directions, for example in the case of a fibrous reinforcement, a unit vector $\mathbf{M}(M_R, M_\Theta, M_Z)$ is introduced representing the fibrous reinforcement in the non-deformed configuration, which gives us the direction of the fibrous reinforcement in deformed configuration denoted \mathbf{m} defined by $\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{M}$.

The calculations give:

$$\mathbf{m} = \begin{pmatrix} r' M_R + \lambda_{rz} M_Z \\ \alpha_0 \frac{r}{R} M_\Theta \\ \omega' M_R + \gamma M_Z \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\mathbf{B}\mathbf{m} = \begin{pmatrix} (1 + \lambda_{rz}^2) (r' M_R + \lambda_{rz} M_Z) + (\omega' + \gamma \lambda_{rz}) (\omega' M_R + \gamma M_Z) \\ (\alpha_0 \frac{r}{R})^2 (\alpha_0 \frac{r}{R} M_\Theta) \\ (\omega' + \gamma \lambda_{rz}) (r' M_R + \lambda_{rz} M_Z) + (\omega'^2 + \gamma^2) (\omega' M_R + \gamma M_Z) \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

So when we set:

$$\mathbf{m} = \begin{pmatrix} m_1 \\ m_2 \\ m_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{m} = \begin{pmatrix} n_1 \\ n_2 \\ n_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

The graphic representations of the vectors \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{n} are:

Figure 7. Space Variation of m Vector

Figure 8. Space Variation of n Vector

According to the previous notation, we find:

$$\mathbf{m} \otimes \mathbf{Bm} = \begin{pmatrix} m_1 n_1 & m_1 n_2 & m_1 n_3 \\ m_2 n_1 & m_2 n_2 & m_2 n_3 \\ m_3 n_1 & m_3 n_2 & m_3 n_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{Bm} \otimes \mathbf{m} = \begin{pmatrix} n_1 m_1 & n_1 m_2 & n_1 m_3 \\ n_2 m_1 & n_2 m_2 & n_2 m_3 \\ n_3 m_1 & n_3 m_2 & n_3 m_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{m} \otimes \mathbf{m} = \begin{pmatrix} m_1^2 & m_1 m_2 & m_1 m_3 \\ m_2 m_1 & m_2^2 & m_2 m_3 \\ m_3 m_1 & m_3 m_2 & m_3^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

We can then calculate the anisotropic elementary invariants of deformation:

$$I_4 = \mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{m} = m_1^2 + m_2^2 + m_3^2;$$

$$I_5 = \mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{Bm} = m_1 n_1 + m_2 n_2 + m_3 n_3$$

The behaviours of these three anisotropic invariants are set by the following graphic:

Figure 9. Forth Anisotropic Invariant

Figure 10. Anisotropic Invariants

We can see here that I_4 stays positive and I_5 stays negative, we have I_4 negligible compared to I_5 in term of absolute value.

ISOTROPIC CASE

It should be noted that the elementary invariants allows us to obtain the energy potential W also called the deformation energy function which is a function of these invariants ($W(I_1, I_2, I_3)$). This function translates the mechanical and/or thermodynamic behavior of the arterial affected by stenosis.

Let's now choose as a potential that of Diouf-Zidi [10] which is summarized in the compressible and isotrope case by:

$$W = \frac{\mu}{2} \left[(I_1 - 3) + a_1 (I_2 - 3) + a_2 \left((I_3^{1/p} - 1)^p + (2 - p) (I_3 - 1) \right) + a_3 \frac{2-p}{1+p} \ln(I_3) \right] \quad (14)$$

where μ , a_1 , a_2 , p and a_3 are material parameters.

A simulation of W for $0.001m \leq r \leq 0.002m$ gives:

Figure 11. Graphic of Isotropic Potential

The graphic shows the big influence of I_1 and I_2 in the isotropic energy potential behaviour.

For a specific choice of the parameter $p = 1$ and $a_3 = 0$, this previous potential becomes:

$$W = \frac{\mu}{2} [(I_1 - 3) + a_1 (I_2 - 3) + 2a_2 (I_3 - 1)] \quad (15)$$

When we consider now $p \neq 1$ and $a_3 \neq 0$ its then yields us these following partial derivatives:

$$\begin{cases} W_1 = \frac{\mu}{2}; \\ W_2 = \frac{\mu a_1}{2}; \\ W_3 = \frac{\mu}{2} \left(a_2 (I_3)^{\frac{1-p}{p}} + 2 - p + a_3 \frac{2-p}{1+p} (I_3)^{-1} \right) \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where $W_{j(j=1;2;3)} = \partial W / \partial I_j$.

There simulations of the isotropic W_j gives:

Figure 12. Graphic of Isotropic W_1 Potential

Figure 13. Graphic of Isotropic W_2 Potential

Figure 14. Graphic of Isotropic W_3 Potential

Figure 15. Graphic of Isotropic W_j Potential

The graphic representations of the three first partial derivative of W_j show a big influence of W_3 in the isotropic potential.

According to the isotropic case, the stress tensor is given in [8] by the following expression:

$$\Sigma = -PI + \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1B + (I_2W_2 + I_3W_3)I - I_3W_2B^{-1}] \quad (17)$$

after replacing in the stress tensor the corresponding expressions, we find the following:

$$\begin{cases} \Sigma_{rr} = -P + \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1 b_{11} + (I_2 W_2 + I_3 W_3) - I_3 W_2 c_{11}]; \\ \Sigma_{\theta\theta} = -P + \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1 b_{22} + (I_2 W_2 + I_3 W_3) - I_3 W_2 c_{22}]; \\ \Sigma_{zz} = -P + \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1 b_{33} + (I_2 W_2 + I_3 W_3) - I_3 W_2 c_{33}]; \\ \Sigma_{rz} = \Sigma_{zr} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1 b_{13} - I_3 W_2 c_{13}]; \\ \Sigma_{r\theta} = \Sigma_{\theta r} = \Sigma_{\theta z} = \Sigma_{z\theta} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

The simulation of these stress components in isotropic case done separately and together give:

Figure 16. Graphic of Isotropic Σ_{rr}

Figure 17. Graphic of Isotropic $\Sigma_{\theta\theta}$

Figure 18. Graphic of Isotropic Σ_{zz}

Figure 19. Graphic of Isotropic Σ_{rz}

Figure 19. Graphic of Isotropic Σ_{ij}

The graphics show that Σ_{rr} stays negative but $\Sigma_{\theta\theta}$, Σ_{zz} and $\Sigma_{rz} = \Sigma_{zr}$ stay positive. Σ_{zz} is greater than all following by $\Sigma_{\theta\theta}$ and then by Σ_{rz} . In term of absolute value, Σ_{rr} is greater than all.

ANISOTROPIC CASE

Let's consider here the Sambou-Diouf energy potential in [11] defined by:

$$W = \frac{\mu}{2} \left[(I_1 - 3) + a_1 (I_2 - 3) + a_2 (I_3^{1/2} - 1) + a_3 \ln(\sqrt{I_3}) \right] + k_0 \left[\exp(k_1 (I_4 - 1)^n) + \delta \left(\exp(k_2 (I_5 - 1)^{2n}) \right) - (1 + \delta) \right], \quad (19)$$

where μ , a_1 , a_2 , p , a_3 , k_0 , k_1 , k_2 and δ are material parameters.

A simulation of W for $0.001m \leq r \leq 0.002m$ gives:

Figure 20. Graphic of Isotropic Potential

The graphic shows again the big influence of I_1 and I_2 in the anisotropic energy potential behaviour. So the anisotropic contribution (I_4, I_5) have not a big influence in the compotement of W .

So then we obtain:

$$\begin{cases} W_1 = \frac{\mu}{2}; \\ W_2 = \frac{\mu}{2}a_2; \\ W_3 = \frac{\mu}{4I_3} (a_2\sqrt{I_3} + a_3); \\ W_4 = nk_0k_1(I_4 - 1)^{n-1} \exp(k_1(I_4 - 1)^n); \\ W_5 = 2nk_0k_2\delta(I_5 - 1)^{2n-1} \left(\exp(k_2(I_5 - 1)^{2n}) \right) \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

Figure 21. Graphic of Isotropic W_1 Potential

Figure 22. Graphic of Isotropic W_2 Potential

Figure 23. Graphic of Isotropic W_3 Potential

Figure 23. Graphic of Isotropic W_4 Potential

Figure 25. Graphic of Isotropic W_5 Potential

Figure 26. Graphic of Isotropic W_j Potential

The graphic show that W_1 and W_2 stay constant and positive. W_3 has a small variation with positive and negative values. W_4 remains with the greatest values. W_5 is negative and remains the smaller in values but the bigger in term of absolute value.

The anisotropic stress tensor is given by:

$$\Sigma = -PI + \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1\mathbf{B} + (I_2W_2 + I_3W_3)\mathbf{I} - I_3W_2\mathbf{B}^{-1}] + 2W_4\mathbf{m} \otimes \mathbf{m} + 2W_5(\mathbf{m} \otimes \mathbf{B}\mathbf{m} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{m} \otimes \mathbf{m}). \quad (21)$$

From these last expression, the stress components become:

$$\begin{cases} \Sigma_{rr} = -P + \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1b_{11} + (I_2W_2 + I_3W_3) - I_3W_2c_{11}] + 2W_4m_1^2 + 2W_5(2m_1n_1); \\ \Sigma_{\theta\theta} = -P + \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1b_{22} + (I_2W_2 + I_3W_3) - I_3W_2c_{22}] + 2W_4m_2^2 + 2W_5(2m_2n_2); \\ \Sigma_{zz} = -P + \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1b_{33} + (I_2W_2 + I_3W_3) - I_3W_2c_{33}] + 2W_4m_3^2 + 2W_5(2m_3n_3); \\ \Sigma_{r\theta} = \Sigma_{\theta r} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1b_{12} - I_3W_2c_{12}] + 2W_4m_1m_2 + 2W_5(m_1n_2 + n_2m_1); \\ \Sigma_{rz} = \Sigma_{zr} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1b_{13} - I_3W_2c_{13}] + 2W_4m_1m_3 + 2W_5(m_1n_3 + n_1m_3); \\ \Sigma_{\theta z} = \Sigma_{z\theta} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1b_{23} - I_3W_2c_{23}] + 2W_4m_2m_3 + 2W_5(m_2n_3 + n_2m_3). \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

Figure 27. Graphic of Isotropic Σ_{rr}

Figure 29. Graphic of Isotropic Σ_{zz}

Figure 31. Graphic of Isotropic Σ_{rz}

Figure 28. Graphic of Isotropic $\Sigma_{\theta\theta}$

Figure 30. Graphic of Isotropic $\Sigma_{r\theta}$

Figure 32. Graphic of Isotropic $\Sigma_{\theta z}$

Figure 33. Graphic of Isotropic Σ_{ij}

The graphics show that Σ_{rr} , Σ_{rz} and $\Sigma_{r\theta}$ stay positive with Σ_{rz} greater than Σ_{zz} which is also greater than Σ_{rr} .

$\Sigma_{\theta\theta}$, $\Sigma_{r\theta}$ and $\Sigma_{\theta z}$ stay negative with $\Sigma_{\theta\theta}$ greater than $\Sigma_{\theta z}$ which is also greater than $\Sigma_{r\theta}$.

We can note a big difference of resistance between isotropic and anisotropic stress components.

RESULT

Study shows a big result between isotropic and anisotropic model:

- The anisotropic contribution has not a big influence in the energy potential behaviour between the two studied models.

- The anisotropic contribution has big influence in the stress components behaviour between the two models.

- The fibrous reinforcement has a big influence in the capacity of resistance of stress components which is true in the reality.

CONCLUSION

In this study of anisotropic contribution in an artery affected by aneurysm in shearing, a kinematic of deformation describing those transformations obtained from the previous studies is given in the case of an isotropic and compressible model. Some tensor and isotropic and anisotropic elementary invariants and stress components needed in this study were calculated.

With a shear which decreases with the progression of the aneurysm, we obtain:

All isotropic invariants positive and I_3 is negligible compared to I_1 and I_2 with I_1 greater than I_2 almost all the time excepted some values where its are equal.

Anisotropic invariant I_4 stays positive and anisotropic invariant I_5 stays negative, we have I_4 negligible compared to I_5 in term of absolute value.

The graphics show the big influence of I_1 and I_2 and W_3 in the isotropic energy potential behaviour. And that Σ_{rr} stays negative but $\Sigma_{\theta\theta}$, Σ_{zz} and $\Sigma_{rz} = \Sigma_{zr}$ stay positive. Σ_{zz} is greater than all following by $\Sigma_{\theta\theta}$ and then by Σ_{rz} . In term of absolute value, Σ_{rr} is greater than all.

The graphics show again the big influence of I_1 and I_2 in the anisotropic energy potential behaviour compared with anisotropic contribution (I_4, I_5). W_1 and W_2 stay constant, positive and negligible. W_3 has a small positive and negative variation values. W_4 remains with the greatest values. W_5 is negative and remains the smaller in values but the bigger in term of absolute value. We can also see that Σ_{rr} , Σ_{rz} and $\Sigma_{r\theta}$ stay positive with Σ_{rz} greater than Σ_{zz} which is also greater than Σ_{rr} .

$\Sigma_{\theta\theta}$, $\Sigma_{r\theta}$ and $\Sigma_{\theta z}$ stay negative with $\Sigma_{\theta\theta}$ greater than $\Sigma_{\theta z}$ which is also greater than $\Sigma_{r\theta}$.

Finally our big contribution in this study is that we show that the anisotropic contribution has not a big influence in the energy potential behaviour, but it has big influence in the stress components behaviour between the two models and then the fibrous reinforcement has a big influence in the capacity of resistance of arterial stress components which is true in the reality.

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